

CANCER TREATMENT WITH MAGNETIC NANOPARTICLES**Mirzayeva Gulnara Elshan gizi***Bachelor's degree in Biotechnology from**Baku State University*

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Abstract

People around the world are turning their attention to inquiry and the process of scientific methodology. Recent years have witnessed a rapid growth in nanoscience research. Nanotechnology applied to medicine and dentistry is expected to bring significant advances in the diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of diseases. The growing interest in the future medical applications of nanotechnology has contributed to the emergence of a new field called nanomedicine. Thanks to medical robots, doctors can quickly cure the most common diseases that today bewilder and kill people, quickly restore most physical injuries in the body, and significantly extend the life span of people. One of the most promising applications of nanobiotechnology in medicine is in diagnostics. Nanoscale materials such as quantum dots, gold nanoparticles, and carbon nanotubes offer excellent opportunities for detecting biomolecules and disease markers with unprecedented sensitivity and specificity. These nanomaterials can be designed to selectively bind to target molecules, allowing the development of ultrasensitive biosensors for early disease detection. One notable example is the use of liposomal nanoparticles to deliver chemotherapy drugs directly to cancer cells while sparing healthy tissue. Cancer is one of the most challenging diseases facing medical research today. Metastatic cancers are not only treated with curative treatments, but also with treatments that often have adverse effects. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), cancer killed 7.9 million people in 2007, making it the leading cause of death worldwide. It is expected that the number of cancer deaths will reach 12 million by 2030. Therefore, the frontiers of cancer research are constantly being tested to develop the most effective tools for diagnosing and treating cancer. The findings from cancer research will in turn benefit humanity and save countless lives.

Keywords: Iron, radiotherapy, gene therapy, thermal ablation, magnetic nanoparticles.

Introduction. Nanotechnology, and in particular the use of magnetic and gold nanoparticles composed of nickel, cobalt, and iron, is leading to major advances. The greatest potential is in drug delivery: magnetic nanoparticles are activated by binding to various substances, including chemotherapeutic agents, radionuclides, nucleic acids, and antibodies. They can then be directed and accumulated using a magnetic field.

The main feature that distinguishes MNPs from other drug nanocarriers is the ability to influence them with an external electromagnetic field and use them in various methods and approaches of biomedical radioelectronics. This effect can provide control over the movement of nanoparticles and their accumulation in target local areas of the body, and if necessary, their significant heating (in the hyperthermia method). From the point of view of the classification of magnetic properties, MNPs are ferro- or ferrimagnets that exhibit superparamagnetic properties due to single-domain properties at sufficiently high temperatures (above the so-called blocking temperature). MNPs based on iron oxides, magnetite (Fe_3O_4) and maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) are most suitable for medical applications, since nanophase iron oxides are widely distributed in living systems due to their low toxicity and can be metabolized by cells. Biogenic magnetic nanoparticles of iron oxide (magnetite and maghemite) are currently found in various living organisms and play an important physiological role, allowing the organism to navigate in the Earth's magnetic field (magnetosomes in bacteria, insects, fish, birds, etc.), as well as a consequence and manifestation of pathologies, especially in humans their presence is associated with neurodegenerative diseases.

Iron oxide-based MNPs are often referred to as superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs), i.e., the characteristic property of these nanoparticles is superparamagnetism. In recent decades, SPIONs have become increasingly popular due to their numerous biomedical applications, such as magnetically mediated hyperthermia cancer therapy, targeted drug delivery, iron replacement therapy, and MRI. Although SPIONs are generally considered biocompatible and have low cytotoxic potential, it is clear that these particles are still foreign bodies in the human body and can exert various effects on the immune system, resulting in hypersensitivity, immunosuppression, or, conversely, immune stimulation.

Typically, medical applications of MNPs are considered either therapeutic or diagnostic. For each specific practical medical task, MNPs are modified, i.e., functionalized, to improve existing ones or to acquire specific properties.

Since conventional chemotherapy is administered systemically, it often causes adverse reactions such as nausea, hair loss, and bone marrow damage, as well as liver and kidney toxicity. These aspects determine the dose of chemotherapeutic agents and limit their effect on the tumor. Therefore, in recent years, there has been a trend in cancer pharmacotherapy to identify agents with higher specificity. Targeted blockade of a specific signaling pathway has led to the creation of genetically mutated cancer cells that can overcome this blockage by up-regulation of an effective parallel, alternative, or overlapping pathway. This leads to the reuse of a broad spectrum of drugs. The biodistribution of these agents is of particular importance for targeted therapy. Nanotechnology can be used to deliver drugs to the intended

site of action with great precision. [1]

Magnetic nanoparticles open up the possibility of using local enhancement methods so that the drug can accumulate and act in a previously defined area. This method was first described in 1978. It is based on the use of three elements: iron (Fe), cobalt (Co) and nickel (Ni). Although all are ferromagnetic under physiological conditions, they do not exhibit the same magnetization: Ni 55 emu/g, Co 160 emu/g and Fe 218 emu/g. They are mainly used as hybrids with other metal ions, oxygen or carbon dioxide. There are countless possibilities for such compounds. Iron compounds are mainly used due to their biocompatibility. They have the lowest toxicity. To prevent agglomeration, ensure stability and positively affect biodistribution, the nanoparticles are coated. Various materials can be used for this, including fatty acids, polyethylene glycol (PEG), dextran and chitosan. Magnetic nanoparticles can carry a variety of different substances and molecules, such as chemotherapeutic agents, antibodies, nucleic acids, radionuclides, etc. In principle, this approach can be used for any tumor, regardless of its size, differentiation, or location. Nanoparticles composed of nickel, cobalt, or iron can be manipulated by a magnetic field due to their ferromagnetism. Iron oxide nanoparticles are particularly used in biomedicine. However, the magnetic force on these particles decreases very rapidly with increasing distance. As a result, it is difficult to target magnetic nanoparticles to tumors deep in the body using an external magnetic field, making therapy difficult [12]

Cancer treatment using magnetic nanoparticles for drug delivery. Nanoparticles used in drug delivery can also increase drug stability and overcome problems associated with the administration of traditional anti-cancer therapies. For example, superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPION) functionalized with PEG and conjugated with doxorubicin (SPIO-PEG-D) have been developed for chemotherapy. In vitro experiments have shown that SPIO-PEG-D results in decreased DNA expression and increased cell apoptosis for HT-29 cancer cells. Furthermore, in vivo experiments have shown that cardiotoxic and hepatotoxic side effects are reduced due to the combination of this drug delivery system and an external magnetic field. MNPs are polymers created with the ability to release drugs or cleavable binders onto drug molecules to achieve controlled and specific drug release. These MNPs can be targeted to a specific site by applying an external magnetic field, and drugs can be delivered by enzymatic degradation or modification in physiological environments such as temperature or pH. For example, nanoparticles have been synthesized with methotrexate and dendrimer-doxorubicin, which are attached to their surface via amide or cleavable hydrazone bonds. Therefore, when the nanoparticles enter cells, the bonds are cleaved by the presence of lysozymes. Through passive targeting, nanoparticles improve the delivery of doxorubicin to the tumor site, and drug release occurs only at lysosomal pH.

Targeted delivery methods are divided into two categories: passive and active. Active methods require an external energy source to direct the nanoparticles to their target site. The effectiveness of a targeted delivery

method depends on various variables. For example, the injection procedure, MNP concentration, hydrodynamic conditions, magnetic field properties, MNPs (including drug particles attached), and the location and depth of the target site. One of the main issues with the application of MNPs is the depth to which the magnetic field can penetrate. The magnetic field can penetrate the body up to 2 cm through the skin without difficulty (Figure 1.2), but it is difficult to penetrate the body beyond 2 cm because the magnetic field decreases with distance. However, internal magnets can be placed near the tumor through minimally invasive surgery to avoid the limitations of external magnetic fields. As with all biomedical applications, there are issues with extrapolating data from animal models to humans. There are many physiological measures that make this difficult, such as weight and physiological changes in the heart. However, given the accessibility of nanoparticles to specific tumor sites compared to traditional surgery, there is still great interest in this area. [6,11]

Silicate nanoparticles with yttrium and vanadium cores and the antitumor drug doxorubicin, which are released in a pH-dependent manner, have been used to treat cancer cells. An additional cytotoxic effect can be achieved by applying an alternating magnetic field after the addition of iron oxide nanoparticles. Fang and co-workers presented a formulation with iron oxide nanoparticles, poly- β -amino-ester-copolymer and doxorubicin, with which they were able to achieve higher uptake and greater toxicity in the treatment of glioma cells compared to the pure drug. By coating magnetic iron particles with β -cyclodextrin and F127 polymer, Yal-lapu et al. also modified the release of the encapsulated drug, resulting in better therapeutic efficacy against cancer.

Magnetic drug targeting (MDT) for cancer treatment is a specific form of drug delivery that uses chemotherapeutic agents directly bound to superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles. The resulting suspension (ferrofluid) is injected directly into an artery supplying the tumor. The particles are concentrated in the tumor by the external magnetic field of the drug. These iron oxide nanoparticles have also been tested in vitro. Therapeutically relevant concentrations have not shown toxicity. An electromagnet with a strong magnetic field gradient of up to 72 T/m at the pole tip and a high magnetic flux density was specially designed for this purpose. Studies in rabbits have demonstrated the accumulation of nanoparticles with the anticancer drug mitoxantrone on histology, MRI, X-ray microtomography (μ CT), and high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). The application of an external magnetic field increased the uptake of nanoparticles per gram of tissue by 114 times in the tumor and surrounding tissue, as demonstrated by quantitative analysis with 59 Fe-labeled ferrofluid. Detailed imaging of the vascular supply is essential for targeted arterial injection. An interventional angiography system, which can provide both 2D and 3D imaging, is best suited for this purpose. After successful treatment, complete regression of both the blood vessels supplying the tumor and the tumor itself has been observed. Antibodies. Since antibody therapy sometimes has significant limitations, efforts

have been made to improve this type of therapy by using drug delivery. By combining antibodies with magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles, cancer cells circulating in the blood of patients with carcinoma have been detected. Another method uses nanoimmunoliposomes. Superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles have been encapsulated in nanosized cationic liposomes with surface fragments of an antibody to the transferrin receptor, which is overexpressed in cancer cells. These approaches are not direct therapeutic approaches, but may allow for early diagnosis and prevention of relapse. [7].

Radiotherapy. Iron oxide nanoparticles have been used to sensitize cancer cells to radiotherapy in vitro. Higher concentrations of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in cells following nanoparticle administration improve the response to radiation.

Gene therapy. Gene therapy has great potential in the treatment of cancer. The malignancy of a cell can ultimately be attributed to “dysfunctional genes”. There is a lack of suitable delivery vehicles known as vectors, but magnetic nanoparticles can also be used here. The method is called magnetofection, which is the targeted transfection of cells with nucleic acids attached to magnetic nanoparticles with the help of a magnetic field. Studies have used magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles to deliver siRNA directly to cancer cells. By combining the technique with a magnet, significantly higher gene delivery efficiency has been demonstrated compared to other transfection reagents. Magnetofection has already been used in numerous studies in vivo; for example, the use of magnetic nanoparticles to improve the uptake of transfected monocytes into tumors is an example. Significant improvements have been found in cell cultures and in mice bearing solid tumors. In their study, Planck and colleagues injected plasmid DNA (encoding a cytokine) bound to magnetic nanoparticles directly into the tumor (fibrosarcoma in cats) and immobilized it there using a magnet. In this way, they activated the immune system against the tumor and reduced the likelihood of recurrence after surgery. They called the procedure Magnetovax (Figure 1.4). A recent study used cobalt carbide nanoparticles. These cobalt nanoparticles, surrounded by carbon shells, showed good biotolerance and provided another means for delivering target-specific genes.

Magnetic nanoparticles. Magnetic nanoparticles can be used for local hyperthermia, as they can be heated by the application of an alternating magnetic field. The heating rate of magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles depends not only on the strength and frequency of the applied alternating field, but also on the size of the particles used.

Scientists have shown in their studies that the in vitro effects of nanoparticles heated by ultrasonic sound (350 kHz) depend on the exposure time and concentration of the nanoparticles. However, Rodriguez-Luccioni showed in a comparative study that in vitro cell viability was significantly affected by magnetic hyperthermia than by heating in a water bath, which suggests that magnetic hyperthermia may have an additional effect on the viability of tumor cells. In their study, a minimum tumor size was determined for effective hyperthermia with an alternating magnetic field.

To facilitate the effects of hyperthermia, a minimum tumor volume of 1 mm³ was determined, consisting of cells that bind magnetic nanoparticles. It was hypothesized that the alternating magnetic field causes mechanical cell damage by activating intracellular iron oxide nanoparticles.

Thermal ablation. In related studies, Kale and colleagues were able to heat nickel nanoparticles to 75°C in vitro for 2 minutes, which is very promising for their use in hyperthermia or thermal ablation. Direct injection of magnetic nanoparticles into tumors or intravenously followed by exposure to an alternating magnetic field has shown anticancer effects in mice. Hyperthermia alone with superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles heated by an alternating magnetic field is already being used to treat cancer. This thermotherapy has been used in a phase I clinical trial to treat patients with prostate cancer. Hyperthermia in combination with radiotherapy has also been used in patients with recurrent glioblastoma.

Baseline MRI (A: coronal; B: sagittal). Particles visible as hyperdense spots after CT scan enhancement. The brown line indicates the tumor size, the other lines indicate the calculated temperature between 40°C (blue) and 50°C (red) (C: coronal; D: sagittal). 3D reconstructions showing the tumor (brown), guided magnetic nanoparticles (blue), and thermometry catheter (green) (E: coronal; D: sagittal).

Hyperthermia is a gradual increase in temperature to 40–43° C. It leads to the destruction of cancer cells and improves the results of chemotherapy and radiation. The disadvantage of this approach is that it does not heat the cancer cells locally. However, this problem can be circumvented by intravenous administration of MNPs targeted to specific areas and the use of an external magnetic field to generate local heat.

Magnetic hyperthermia is a non-invasive approach to cancer treatment. This approach offers an alternative for some cancers that are difficult to remove surgically and those that are close to vital organs. Because magnetic hyperthermia overcomes the issue of non-selective ionizing radiation associated with traditional radiotherapy, treatment options may extend beyond certain tumors. Magnetite and maghemite are the most commonly used nanoparticle materials for magnetic hyperthermia.

Magnetite is one of the most important magnetic materials due to its high saturation magnetization and its ability to easily functionalize biomolecules. Magnetic hyperthermia relies on raising the temperature at the tumor site to 41–47°C for induction of apoptosis or to 50°C for induction of necrosis. Temperatures up to 42°C can be referred to as mild hyperthermia, while temperatures above this can be referred to as extreme hyperthermia. The heat from high temperatures can cause changes in cell membrane permeability, stimulation of the immune system, denaturation of proteins, cytoskeletal damage, and disruption of specific DNA repair processes. By using an environment similar to the tumor microenvironment, magnetic hyperthermia has been shown to require a target temperature approximately 6 °C lower than exogenous hyperthermia to achieve an equivalent cell death effect. It also exerts a

more significant cytotoxic effect. Cancer cells are thought to be more sensitive to heat than healthy cells due to their increased metabolic rate. At the tissue level, the tumor's ability to dissipate heat is reduced because its vascular system is compromised. Increased temperature also increases cellular sensitivity to alternative therapies such as chemotherapy and radiation. Moreover, the increased sensitivity of cancer cells may be attributed to the enhanced antitumor immune response induced by hyperthermia, due to its ability to enhance the presentation of tumor antigens, leukocyte trafficking across the endothelium, and activation of NK cells and dendritic cells. The degree of sensitivity depends on the time elapsed between heat and chemotherapy, the nature and concentration of the drug, the tumor type, and the tumor temperature. Hyperthermia treatment induces certain biological effects within cancer cells, such as enhanced lysosomal permeability, which in turn results in increased oxidative stress due to the production of reactive oxygen species. Reduced tumor cell viability through enhanced cathepsin D activity in the cytoplasm is another consequence of increased lysosomal permeability. Furthermore, the rotation of SPIONs induced by dynamic magnetic fields can disrupt lipid membrane stability, thereby affecting lysosomal permeability and leading to the activation of apoptosis.

The SAR value depends on the frequency and amplitude of the magnetic field, the shape and size of the particles, and their magnetic properties. One study reported that graphene oxide-tunable magnetic nanorods applied in mouse models were effective for hyperthermia. 350 nm nanorods had the highest SAR value of 1045 W g at an iron concentration of 0.2 mg mL⁻¹ among three different nanorods used (250, 350, and 460 nm). 350 nm nanorods demonstrated adequate tumor volume reduction in the mouse model and showed favorable biocompatibility in the MTT assay. The intrinsic damage parameter (ILP) is an additional concept to consider. Several investigators have started reporting ILP instead of SAR because it eliminates the effects of field and frequency in the calculation. ILP is considered stable only under low field strength and low frequency measurements. Consequently, it is not recommended to use ILP as a means of comparison between studies. In order to successfully compare the SAR values of samples, the field, frequency, media, and measured concentration must all be kept constant.[4; 8].

Recently, *in vivo* experiments have been conducted to investigate the effect of magnetic hyperthermia on tumor size. A group of researchers used superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles coated with carboxydextran for magnetic hyperthermia. BALB/c nu/nu athymic mice injected with non-small cell lung cancer cell line A549 cells were exposed to a varying magnetic field for 20 minutes. Significant reductions in tumor size were reported. Accordingly, the researchers injected the pancreatic cancer cell line Pan02 cells into mice to synthesize pancreatic cancer tissue. Iron oxide nanoparticles loaded on monocyte/macrophage-like cells were injected into the mice after tumor growth. After three days, the MNPs found in the cancer tissue generated heat when exposed to a varying magnetic

field. After a certain period of time, a significant reduction in tumor size was observed. In addition, it has recently been shown that hyperthermia helps eliminate cancer stem cell populations, which are an important cause of metastasis and cancer recurrence. This may be due to the production of reactive oxygen species. [9,10]

These issues can be addressed by using a non-contact stimulus that localizes heat induction and by enhancing real-time temperature control. Magnetic resonance thermometry (MRT) is a successful non-invasive MRI-based technique that involves measuring temperature distributions in 3D, potentially replacing the current use of invasive thermal probes. The use of MRI in combination with thermometry was proposed 40 years ago. MRI techniques have since improved their accuracy for *in vivo* and preclinical development. To further increase their effectiveness and avoid undesirable side effects, new non-invasive targeted heat sources for hyperthermia have been investigated. Although a single device that allows for both hyperthermia and *in vivo* localization simultaneously would be cost-effective, the alternating magnetic field requirements between MRI and hyperthermia prohibit real-time guidance.[2]

Overcoming cancer drug resistance with magnetic nanoparticles. Causes of drug resistance.

Surgery is still the gold standard of treatment for most solid tumors. At the time of diagnosis, the disease is no longer confined to local growth, but 50% of patients already have metastases. Therefore, surgery can no longer offer a curative treatment. The currently available options, radiotherapy and chemotherapy, also have their limitations. The tumor may be located in areas that are difficult for drugs to reach or are protected by other mechanisms, such as high hydrostatic pressure in the tissue or poor vascular supply. In addition, some types of cancer are not sensitive to radiation or anti-cancer drugs. One of the biggest problems is the resistance to a particular therapy that develops during treatment. This is usually the cause of recurrence after radio or chemotherapy. Here, ATP-binding cassette (ABC) transporters are of particular importance. They are responsible for the simultaneous resistance to several different chemotherapeutic agents (multidrug resistance), as they remove these toxic substances from the cells. Other mechanisms include enhanced DNA repair, effects on the cell cycle, and altered intracellular drug metabolism. [5]

Magnetic nanoparticles against cancer drug resistance. Nanotechnology allows for the combination of different substances and mechanisms of action, as well as their targeted use. Magnetic nanoparticles are coated with biocompatible materials and functionalized with one or more different active ingredients. Therefore, it is possible to use different therapeutic mechanisms simultaneously, which greatly reduces the possibility of resistance. For example, Tang and co-workers used magnetic nanoparticles with manganese, zinc and iron oxide cores, as well as human albumin, folic acid, cisplatin and the radionuclide 188 rhenium. In this way, the triple effect of radiotherapy, chemotherapy and hyperthermia can be achieved. They tested the pharmacokinetics and biodistribution *in vivo* in a tumor-bearing nude mouse model (human ovarian cancer SKOV3

cells in 21 BALB/C nude mice). Another possibility is to increase the concentration of the anticancer drug to a level at which no malignant cells survive. For this purpose, a magnetic field is of great importance for tissue-specific enrichment of magnetic nanoparticles and the drug attached to them. This strategy is used, for example, in MDT, as previously described. Even tumors that are resistant to treatment can be more effectively penetrated by magnetic nanoparticles. One strategy is, for example, the simultaneous combination of an anticancer drug and a drug that targets the resistance mechanism. In vitro cytotoxicity testing of doxorubicin in K562/A02 cells (a human chronic myeloid leukemia resistant cell line) showed a significant effect on the cells compared to an antineoplastic agent bound to nanoparticles without an ABC transporter inhibitor. Agents that are not affected by the relevant resistance mechanism or that directly target it (e.g., antibodies against ABC transporters) could be used.[3]

Conclusion. Magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) are a revolutionary approach in cancer treatment. They enhance the efficacy of chemotherapy by targeting drug delivery and reduce its side effects. MNPs can be controlled by an external magnetic field and can provide hyperthermic destruction of tumor cells. Superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs) play a particularly important role because they exhibit low cytotoxicity and high biocompatibility. These nanoparticles can be combined with antibodies, gene therapy, and radionuclides to further enhance the effectiveness of the treatment. Thanks to the development of nanotechnology, the properties of nanoparticles that reduce drug resistance have also been studied. In addition, non-invasive temperature control with magnetic resonance thermometry (MRT) can be provided, allowing hyperthermia treatment to be performed more precisely and safely. Research is still ongoing for the wider application of MNPs in cancer treatment, and advances in this area may enable more effective and personalized therapies in the future.

In addition to the basic and biocompatible coating, a functionalized nanoparticle should ideally have four components to perform various tasks:

1. Antitumor effects;

This effect is achieved by the association of substances that directly act on the tumor, such as chemotherapeutic agents, nucleic acids, radionuclides, etc. This heading also includes the induction of hyperthermia using an alternating magnetic field.

2. Overcoming resistance to cancer drugs;

Nanoparticles are combined with substances that aim to provide effective therapy by inhibiting tumor drug resistance. ABC transporter inhibitors or antibodies are considered here.

3. Diagnostic studies and imaging;

Functionalized nanoparticles should include a substance used for diagnostic purposes. This would allow combining therapy and diagnostic research with "theranostics". Magnetic nanoparticles are already used as contrast agents in magnetic resonance imaging.

4. Targeted site enhancement.

It is possible to concentrate nanoparticles at the desired site and combine them with antibodies that specifically bind to the tumor to target the tumor. Another option is to assemble magnetic nanoparticles using a magnetic field.

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